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GLOBAL MIGRATION TRENDS, ITS CAUSES AND CONSEQUENCES FOR THE COUNTRY IN THE CONTEXT OF GLOBALIZATION

СВІТОВІ ТЕНДЕНЦІЇ МІГРАЦІЇ, ЇЇ ПРИЧИНИ ТА НАСЛІДКИ ДЛЯ ДЕРЖАВИ В УМОВАХ ГЛОБАЛІЗАЦІЇ

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Добрянська Н.А., Галицький О.М., Макодзьоб А.В. Світові тенденції міграції, її причини та наслідки для держави в умовах глобалізації. Оглядова стаття.

У статті досліджено нелегальну міграцію та політику держави щодо її усунення. Визначено поняття нелегальної міграції: передумови виникнення та її ознаки. Обґрунтовано причини нелегальної міграції та її наслідки. Визначено державну політику України щодо протидії нелегальної міграції: безпекові аспекти. Основний науковий результат роботи полягає в тому, що неконтрольовані міграційні процеси є загрозою національним інтересам. Шляхом аналізу впливу міграції на національну безпеку нашої держави, доведено, що основними недоліками державної міграційної політики щодо боротьби з неконтрольованою міграцією є недостатня кількість фахівців та експертів у сфері міграції, а також те, що негативні наслідки неконтрольованої міграції в нашій країні ще не проявлялись повною мірою, помилки у визначенні національних інтересів призводять до державного безладдя, створюють загрозу нації. Крім того, з'ясовано, що загрозу для суспільства становлять біженці, які перебувають у країні нелегально і не реєстровані відповідними органами.

Ключові слова: міграція, нелегальність, держава, політика, наслідки, країна, загроза, безпека

Dobrianska N.A., Halytskyi O.M., Makodzeb A.V. Global migration trends, its causes and consequences for the country in the context of globalization. Review article.

The article examines illegal migration and the government's policy to eliminate it. The concept of illegal migration is defined: the prerequisites for its occurrence and its signs. The reasons for illegal migration and its consequences have been substantiated. The state policy of Ukraine regarding countering illegal migration has been determined: security issues aspects. The main scientific result of the work is that uncontrolled migration processes are a threat to national interests. By analyzing the impact of migration on the national security of our state, it has been proved that the main drawbacks of the state migration policy to combat uncontrolled migration are the insufficient number of specialists and experts in the field of migration, as well as the fact that the negative consequences of uncontrolled migration in our country have not yet fully manifested themselves. To a lesser extent, mistakes in defining national interests lead to state disorder and pose a threat to the nation. In addition, it has been established that refugees who are in the country illegally and are not registered by the relevant authorities constitute a threat to society.

Keywords: migration, illegalities, state, policy, consequences, country, threat, security

Migratory movements, which are characterized by considerable scale, have become an important factor in the development of a globalized world. They affect the formation of quantitative and qualitative composition of the population, socio-demographic and economic development, political and cultural spheres. The analysis of current migration trends in our country, which are characterized by massive interstate migration movements in the context of Ukraine's participation in the world migration space is regarded as an important factor in shaping national policy. This topic is in the plane of the security environment of Ukraine and provides research and solutions to current security issues related to the migration space of Ukraine and mass external migration movements.

Analysis of recent research and publications

In the work on this research we used the works of key specialists in migration issues in Ukraine, in particular: O. Malinovskaya, A. Shlepakov, V. Kosevtsov, Y. Kalinovsky, V. Troshchinsky. The study also analyzed the

current legal framework for the regulation of migration processes, ethno-national policy and national security, which is currently formed in Ukraine.

The aim of the article is to analyze the current state of illegal migration policy in Ukraine security and proposals for measures to prevent illegal migration through the territory of Ukraine. The subject of the research is the theoretical principles, state and prospects of state regulation of illegal migration in Ukraine.

The main part

Illegal migration is an integral part of a well-known phenomenon, denoted by the term "population migration".

The term "migration" comes from the Latin "migrate, migro", ie relocation, resettlement. The main features of migration are:

- movement of people, resettlement, movement, i.e. – the process;
- crossing in the process of moving state or administrative boundaries of territories;
- temporary or permanent change of place of residence or work;
- improvement of socio-economic condition.

Thus, according to the legality of stay, migration is: legal and illegal.

Legal migration is the crossing of international borders and stay in the country on legal grounds. Such migrants enter the country with an entry visa or other legal grounds, stay in the country for a certain period of time [1].

Illegal migration is characterized by the fact that its subjects leave the country of residence and enter territories of other states without official permission.

The emergence and spread of illegal migration has led to interest from politicians, legal scholars, members of the media, the general public. The term "illegal migration" began to be actively used in normative materials, scientific publications, analytical materials, journalistic publications, popular science literature, newspapers, magazines and other mass media, at symposia, conferences, "round tables".

Illegal (illegal) migration is illegal movement across the state border, i.e. outside checkpoints or with concealment from border and customs control, using forged documents, visas (or without a visa), alone or with the help of third parties, and as well as living in the country without the proper permission of the competent state authorities.

The presence of illegal migrants causes not only social and political complications, but also direct economic damage. Given the statistics on the number of detected illegal migrants, there is reason to believe that in recent years the city of Kyiv annually spends more than 2 million US dollars on their maintenance [2].

According to the State Border Guard Service of Ukraine, the number of illegal migrants is not decreasing. Moldovans, Georgians and Russian Chechens are trying to use Ukraine as a transit country for migration, trying to find new ways to cross the Ukrainian border illegally.

Human trafficking remains a problem. Criminals use illegal migration. The International Organization for Migration notes an increase in the number of victims of human trafficking in Ukraine. It is worrying that trafficking in human beings remains a problem for society not only in Ukraine but also in other countries of the world. According to the results of such a study, a rating of countries to combat trafficking was compiled, and Ukraine ranked 87th out of 182. Based on a study by experts from the Universities of Göttingen and Heidelberg, as well as the London School, it was concluded that the best problem with human trafficking in the Netherlands, Sweden, the United States, Slovenia, Belgium and Spain.

This has significant criminal consequences, leaving migrants hostage, forcing them to sell drugs and prostitution.

The ratio of men to women arriving illegally for Ukraine remains the same: men – 75-77%, women – 15-13%. But if in general the ratio of men and women remains more or less constant, then in relation to certain age categories it is differentiated in a wide range. The main conclusion is that the share of women who come to Ukraine illegally decreases with age, i.e. at the age of 55-65 their number is about 2% of the total number of women.

Many women cross the borders of Ukraine illegally. Due to the fact that, according to national customs, they do not have the right to vote, so they do what their husbands or older sons decide, some are forced to become illegal migrants to reunite with their families in order to improve the lives of their children. 1}} Illegal migrants are mostly young men (not older than 30 and more than half single). According to our study, migrants aged 17-20 years – 5.8% of the total number of migrants, 21-25 years – 33.0%, 26-30 years – 25.2%, 31-35 years – 16.2%, 36-40 years – 8.4%, 41-50 years – 1.6%, 51-67 years – 4.4%. Another characteristic feature is the marital status of illegal migrants [3].

There are large differences in the demographic structure of different groups of migrants: 64% of Afghans outnumber married migrants, and more than 68% of Africans and migrants from the Middle East. Table 1 shows the marital status of illegal migrants.

So, analyzing the table, we see that most married people in Afghanistan – 64%. The lowest in African countries – 30%. Divorced in Southeast Asia – 5%. Most widows in the CIS countries – 16%. 79% are unmarried in the Middle East. And in the CIS countries, at least 28% are unmarried.

Table 1. Marital status of illegal migrants, %

Marital status	CIS countries	African countries	Afghanistan	Southeast Asia	Middle East
Married	42	30	64	39	21
Divorced	4	1	–	5	–
Widows	16	1	2	–	–
Not married	28	68	34	56	79
Total	100	100	100	100	100

Source: compiled by authors on materials [3].

Most married migrants (80%) came to Ukraine with their families, including their parents. Every third migrant has children under 10 years old. It should also be noted that families with three or more children who follow their parents – 35%. Large families are mostly Afghans, Kurds, and much fewer Africans. Peculiarities of an illegal migrant are strong family ties and permanent residence [4].

Unequal numbers of illegal migrants come to Ukraine from different regions. Migrants who leave because of political oppression or hostilities leave the country in equal numbers, both under the age of 30 and 30-40, are migrants from Afghanistan and Iraq. Another picture is in the Middle East and Southeast Asia, where migrants are mostly under 30 years old. The majority of migrants from these regions are men – 76%.

Analyzing the data obtained during the interview, we can conclude that migrants arriving in Ukraine from Latin America account for 2% of the total number of illegal migrants, with former republics of the USSR – 13%, the Middle East – 18%, Northeast Asia – 19%, Afghanistan – 21%. Africa – 30% (mainly from Somalia, Zaire, Angola, Congo, Sierra Leone). About 41% of migrants from the CIS are Armenians.

Most migrants come to Ukraine from their countries of birth and 31% from the country of transit. Almost half of illegal migrants were born in the capitals of their countries or large cities. An even larger share of the capital's residents among those who changed their place of residence. This is often due to the fact that in war-torn countries, more tense and dangerous circumstances occur in capitals and large cities [5].

The number of illegal migrants is growing every year. This is evidenced by the statistics of the Ministry of Internal Affairs of Ukraine, the State Border Guard Service of Ukraine, on the applications of illegal migrants to obtain refugee status.

Illegal migration has the same causes as other migrations, but they are more global, tragic, conflictual. It is these reasons that force illegal migrants to risk their own lives, the lives of their families, to commit offenses in order to improve their living conditions, to escape from conflicts. Figure 1 shows the reasons for migration.

Figure 1. The main causes of migration

Source: compiled by authors on materials [5].

The effects of migration may be different for different countries and regions, both for those who provide labor and those who receive it. Therefore, consider the positive and negative effects of migration for emigration and immigration countries [6]. Migration consequences for donor and recipient countries are presented in table 2.

Thus, migration processes have significant social significance, are characterized by current and long-term consequences of positive and negative nature, are influenced by a combination of factors and options of state models of regulation and divide the world into winners and losers. This presupposes a careful attitude towards migration and migrants at the state level, based, on the one hand, on the awareness of the need and possibility of

state regulation and the choice of a certain model of direct influence, and on the other, on the identification of indirect factors such as socio-economic or political.

Table 2. Migration implications for donor and recipient countries

Donor countries	Recipient countries
Positive consequences	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – changing the level and conditions of unemployment in the national labor market, – minimizing the tension of the domestic labor market; – increasing opportunities for effective realization of labor potential; – the ability to gain new knowledge, professional experience and improving the skills of migrants, – increasing the return on individual investment in education; – the inflow of migrants' cash; – improving the financial situation of migrant families; – tax on profits of intermediary firms; – optimization of the budget burden; – personal investment of migrants; – influx of innovation, international cooperation; – expansion of international social ties; – establishing close ties between countries; – raising the general cultural level of the population. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – optimization of the labor market structure through the sale of vacancies by non-residents in various sectors of the economy, – increasing productivity and efficiency; – improving labor standards; – optimization of investment resources in the training of specialists in various fields, in the implementation of academic research; – improving the demographic situation; – increasing tax revenues from migrants; – information flows and cooperation with donor countries, – increasing export opportunities; – development of cultural diversity and the formation of new integrated cultural values, improving the principles of business ethics.
Negative consequences	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – loss of human potential, both quantitatively and qualitatively, – outflow of intellectual potential; – loss of professional skills and qualifications when working outside the specialty; – reduction return on investment in human capital, education, – reduced productivity and efficiency; – reduction of potential monetary and financial transactions in the domestic market; – possible discrimination of citizens during temporary work abroad, – rising prices in domestic markets with the existing low purchasing power of the majority of the population; – lack of a formal contract leads to insecurity of migrants' labor rights; prospects for the country's development; – loss of national identity, increasing social tensions. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – increasing the burden on the country's social system; – additional burden on the educational and scientific sectors of the economy; – growing budget deficit due to forced additional investments in various sectors of the economy; – transition of legal migration to illegal, conducting covert currency transactions; – possible transfer of new technologies to foreign competitors; – ethnic misunderstandings, socio-cultural conflicts, formation of criminogenic situation in places of compact residence of migrants; – aggravation of the political situation, – increasing the level of possible loss of cultural identity of the nation.

Source: compiled by authors on materials [6].

Illegal migration is a socially dangerous, harmful, illegal phenomenon that really threatens the economic interests and public security of our state. It is one of the reasons for the growth of crime, the spread of dangerous diseases, the development of the underground labor market, the emergence of tensions between many states.

Officials of the State Border Guard Service of Ukraine statelessness from Ukraine. Accordingly, the number of such decisions on average is twice the number of court decisions on forced expulsion. The increase in the use of these powers by administrative courts does not guarantee the result - an increase in the number of illegal migrants who left Ukraine (Fig. 2).

Regulatory procedures "Forced return" and "forced expulsion" belong to the system of administrative and legal measures aimed at forcing foreigners and stateless persons to leave the territory of Ukraine

Forced return of foreigners to the country of origin or third country is based on a decision of the State Migration Service Of Ukraine (hereinafter – LCA of Ukraine), a body of the Security Service of Ukraine (hereinafter - the Security Service of Ukraine) or a body of state border protection on forced return or forced expulsion on the basis of the decision of the administrative court on forced expulsion (Article 26 of the Law of Ukraine "On the legal status of foreigners and stateless persons).

Looking at Figure 2, we can conclude that the and the largest number of people are people who went to enforce decisions on forced return and forced expulsion. The least number of decisions on forced expulsion. The number of decisions on forced return is in second place.

The practice of making a decision on forced return, prior to applying to the administrative court for his forced expulsion, forces the State Border Guard Service of Ukraine to use such powers even when they do not directly provide the proper result is the deprivation of the illegal migrant of the possibility of further stay on the territory of the state.

Figure 2. The ratio of the number of decisions on forced return and forced expulsion, as well as the number of people who went to enforce these decisions
 Source: compiled by authors on materials [7].

Establishing and maintaining the effectiveness of the migration regime is ensured through various processes and regulatory mechanisms, among which, in our opinion, the most effective is the mechanism for combating illegal migration. Thus, it contains the following elements:

- a system of regulations that form the basis of the mechanism,
- organizational and structural formation of the mechanism;
- organizational and legal methods.

A number of public authorities are involved in the formation and implementation of migration policy in Ukraine (Fig. 3), the main of which are:

- Ministry of Internal Affairs of Ukraine – ensures the formation of state policy in the areas of migration (immigration and emigration), including combating illegal (illegal) migration, citizenship, registration of individuals, refugees and other statutory categories of migrants. Detects, terminates and discloses criminal offenses related to illegal migration and trafficking in human beings.
- State Migration Service (LMS) of Ukraine – implements state policy in the areas of migration (immigration and emigration), including combating illegal (illegal) migration, citizenship, registration of individuals, refugees and other statutory categories of migrants. The activities of the Service are directed and coordinated by the Cabinet of Ministers of Ukraine through the Minister of Internal Affairs.
- State Border Guard Service of Ukraine.
- Security Service of Ukraine – conducts pre-trial investigation of crimes related to illegal transportation of persons across the state border of Ukraine, participates in the development of measures and issues related to entry into Ukraine and departure abroad, stay on its territory of foreigners and persons without citizenship, decides on the prohibition of entry into Ukraine of a foreigner or stateless person, on reducing the period of temporary stay of a foreigner and a stateless person on the territory of Ukraine, on the forced return of a foreigner or stateless person to the country of origin or third country.

Figure 3. Structure of the State Migration Service (Representation) as of August 2019
 Source: compiled by authors on materials [7].

The State Migration Service of Ukraine (LCA of Ukraine) is a central executive body whose activities are directed and coordinated by the Cabinet of Ministers of Ukraine through the Minister of Internal Affairs of Ukraine. LCA of Ukraine is part of the system of executive bodies and is formed to implement state policy in the areas of migration (immigration and emigration), including combating illegal (illegal) migration, citizenship, registration of individuals, refugees and others.

April 2011, the Decree of the President of Ukraine dated 06.04.2011 № 405/2011, approved the Regulations on the State Migration Service of Ukraine, which defines the main tasks, functions and powers of the LCA of Ukraine.

In August 2014, the Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of Ukraine № 360 of 20.08.2014, a new Regulation on the State Migration Service of Ukraine was approved.

The existence of problems in the fight against illegal migration, the negative consequences of this process in Ukraine, require the development of effective ways to counter in modern conditions, in particular:

- to further improve the systemic approach to central authorities executive authorities to perform tasks at the state level (MIA, LCA, SBGS);
- identification and closure of the most dangerous channels of migration to Ukraine by improving visa policy and quality of border control, stopping the entry of illegal migrants at the site border with Russia, Belarus, Moldova,
- detection and detection on the territory of Ukraine of criminal groups involved in the organization of smuggling of illegal migrants, production and provision of forged documents;
- determining the procedure for providing transport services to citizens with countries of origin of the largest number of illegal migrants,
- the creation of a single automated system of information support law enforcement agencies in the fight against illegal migration,
- the establishment of an effective mechanism for the expulsion of illegal migrants to their places of residence or to the countries from which they came. To do this, it is necessary to conclude appropriate intergovernmental agreements, create places of temporary detention, attract funds from organizations that profit from the reception of foreigners in Ukraine, and so on.

Summarizing all the above, proposals have been developed to improve migration policy. Taking into account and applying these proposals in practice, in our opinion, will be able to help eliminate the shortcomings that exist today. Suggestions:

- Higher executive bodies need to pay more attention to migration issues. Clarify the functions of agencies dealing with migration issues. Clearly define the strategy and tactics in ensuring migration policy by public authorities.
- Development of a mechanism for socio-economic and domestic adaptation of migrants to Ukrainian society.
- It is necessary to provide scientific substantiation of implementations in the field of migration processes, focusing on Western European and world experience. Preservation and protection of scientific potential. Scientific support of research on migration problems.
- Improving the system of migration statistics. Providing meaningful and accessible online information.
- More active work with international organizations, in particular the OSCE, the UN.

Conclusions

Thus, it follows from the above that there are the following types of illegal migration, namely: external illegal migration; permanent or irreversible illegal migration; seasonal illegal migration; transit illegal migration; illegal emigration; illegal immigration.

Illegal migration occupies an important place in the structure of migration flows. It is a socially dangerous, harmful, illegal phenomenon that really threatens the economic interests and public security of Ukraine. Illegal migration is one of the reasons for the growth of crime, the spread of dangerous diseases, the development of the underground labor market, the emergence of tensions between many states.

Executive authorities work inefficiently. Insufficient attention to the problems of migration, underestimation of its impact on national security may cause significant damage to the national interests of Ukraine in the near future. place of residence or not – a new phenomenon for Ukraine. State control over migration processes, on the one hand, serves to homogenize society, on the other hand, demonstrates external state sovereignty. In this regard, migration policy is an important element of state-building, as well as a means of ensuring state security.

Ukraine does not yet have sufficient experience in state regulation of illegal migration processes. Therefore, today we have one of the important tasks – a well-thought-out development of joint with neighbouring countries comprehensive programs to combat illegal migration.

Abstract

The article examines illegal migration and the government's policy to eliminate it. The concept of illegal migration is defined: the prerequisites for its occurrence and its signs. The reasons for illegal migration and its consequences have been substantiated. The state policy of Ukraine regarding countering illegal migration has been determined: security issues aspects. The main scientific result of the work is that uncontrolled migration

processes are a threat to national interests. By analyzing the impact of migration on the national security of our state, it has been proved that the main drawbacks of the state migration policy to combat uncontrolled migration are the insufficient number of specialists and experts in the field of migration, as well as the fact that the negative consequences of uncontrolled migration in our country have not yet fully manifested themselves. To a lesser extent, mistakes in defining national interests lead to state disorder and pose a threat to the nation. In addition, it has been established that refugees who are in the country illegally and are not registered by the relevant authorities constitute a threat to society. Migratory movements, which are characterized by considerable scale, have become an important factor in the development of a globalized world. They affect the formation of quantitative and qualitative composition of the population, socio-demographic and economic development, political and cultural spheres. The analysis of current migration trends in our country, which are characterized by massive interstate migration movements in the context of Ukraine's participation in the world migration space is regarded as an important factor in the formation of national policy. This topic is in the plane of the security environment of Ukraine and provides research and solutions to current security issues related to the migration space of Ukraine and mass external migration movements. It follows from the above that there are the following types of illegal migration, namely: external illegal migration; permanent or irreversible illegal migration; seasonal illegal migration; transit illegal migration; illegal emigration; immigration illegal migration. Illegal migration occupies an important place in the structure of migration flows. It is a socially dangerous, harmful, illegal phenomenon that really threatens the economic interests and public security of Ukraine. Illegal migration is one of the reasons for the growth of crime, the spread of dangerous diseases, the development of the underground labor market, the emergence of tensions between many countries. The state does not pay enough attention to migration problems, there are significant shortcomings in the legal framework for regulating migration processes, the executive authorities work inefficiently. Insufficient attention to the problems of migration, underestimation of its impact on national security can cause significant damage to the national interests of Ukraine in the near future. Settlement of migration processes in accordance with national interests in conditions when each individual is free to decide whether to change his place of residence or not – a new phenomenon for Ukraine. State control over migration processes, on the one hand, serves to homogenize society, on the other hand, demonstrates external state sovereignty. In this regard, migration policy is an important element of state-building, as well as a means of ensuring state security. Ukraine does not yet have sufficient experience in state regulation of illegal migration processes. Therefore, today we have one of the important tasks – a well-thought-out development of joint with neighbouring countries comprehensive programs to combat illegal migration.

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